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CONTRIBUTION TO THE KNOWLEDGE OF MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF RED DEER ANTLERS (*CERVUS ELAPHUS MONTANUS*, BOTEZAT, 1903) IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

In Europe, the largest wild animal is the red deer (*Cervus elaphus*). It is widespread, practically in all countries on the European continent. Despite numerous efforts that have lasted for decades, a unified zoological systematics of the red deer has not yet been created. The large number of subspecies and varieties complicates this task. One of the varieties that inhabits the territory of Romania (*Cervus elaphus montanus*, Botezat, 1903) (Cotta et al. 2001, Obletenov, 2010, Urošević B.M. 2015) was the subject of our research.

Thirty deer antlers were analyzed, hunted in Romania, and exhibited at a hunting exhibition in Bucharest in 1997. The data was taken from the official catalog. The morphological parameters examined were: the length of the left beam of the antler, the length of the right beam of the antler, the length of the left brow tine, the length of the right brow tine, the length of the left frontal tine, the length of the right frontal tine, and the girth of the left and right coronets.

It was found that the average length of the left beam of the antler is 117.79 cm, and the right one is 115.05 cm. The average length of the left brow tine was 41.62 cm, and the right one was 40.88 cm. Regarding the frontal tine, the average length of the left one was 41.76 cm, and the right one was 40.52 cm. The average value for the girth of the left coronet was 26.98 cm, and the right one was 27.00 cm.

In absolute values, the differences between the arithmetic values for the morphological parameters on the left and right beams are minimal.

Keywords: red deer, trophy antlers, Romania

Introduction

In Europe, the largest wild animal is the red deer (*Cervus elaphus*). It is widespread, practically in all countries on the European continent. Despite numerous efforts that have lasted for decades, a unified zoological systematics of the red deer has not yet been created. The large number of subspecies and varieties complicates this task. One of the varieties that inhabits the territory of Romania (*Cervus elaphus montanus*, Botezat, 1903) (Cotta et al. 2001, Obletenov, 2010, Urošević B.M. 2015) was the subject of our research.

In the available scientific literature, data on the antlers of the Carpathian deer (*Cervus elaphus montanus*, Botezat, 1903) are rare. In the book on hunting in Romania, Cotta et al. (2001) state that deer aged 10-12 years have antlers weighing between 7-15 kg, averaging 8 kg. The authors do not mention any morphometric parameters of the antlers.

In the available literature, there is only one analysis of the morphological parameters of deer hunted in Romania. A detailed analysis of the antlers of

red deer (*Cervus elaphus* L.) hunted in Romania during the period 2017-2018 was conducted by Sirbu et al. (2020). They studied 66 antlers and divided them into three groups based on age. The first group consisted of deer aged 4-6 years, the second of those aged 7-9 years, and the third group included deer older than 10 years. In the first group, the average antler length was 86.87 cm, in the second group 107.01 cm, and in the third 111.18 cm. The average brow tine length in the first group was 30.28 cm, in the second 34.89 cm, and in the third 37.29 cm. Regarding the brow tine, its average length in the first group was 26.57 cm, in the second 32.10 cm, and in the third 34.92 cm. The circumference of the rose had an average value of 19.48 cm in the first group, 24.53 cm in the second, and 25.20 cm in the third group. It is noticeable that as the age of the deer increases, the absolute values of the analyzed parameters also increase.

Studying the antlers of the common deer (*Cervus elaphus*), Dragišić (1957) notes that the record deer trophy at the Düsseldorf exhibition in 1954 had a right

main beam length of 126.00 cm and a left main beam length of 128.80 cm. The length of the right brow tine was 47.20 cm, and the left 50.40 cm. The right frontal tine was 54.40 cm long, and the left 57.60 cm. The author states that mature deer have a rose circumference of 28-32 cm. Rajskey et al. (2003) report that in deer hunted in Slovakia, the average length of the main beam at the age of three years was 56.7 cm, and at four years, it increased to 62.8 cm. At the age of 12 years, deer in Slovakia had an average beam length of 100.8 cm. The authors found that the brow tine, in deer aged three years, had an average length of 17.9 cm, at four years, its average length was 19.7 cm, and at 12 years, the brow tine was on average 36.2 cm long. The rose circumference at the age of three years was 15.2 cm, and at four, it was 17.6 cm. Twelve-year-old deer had an average rose circumference of 26.1 cm.

Analyzing the morphological parameters of deer hunted in mountainous and lowland areas in Serbia, Urošević et al. (2018) found a highly significant statistical difference in the length of the left main beam between individuals from mountainous and lowland hunting grounds. The same statistical significance was found in the length of the right main beam. The average length of the left beam of lowland deer was 100.40±8.20 cm, while in mountainous deer, it was 102.80±9.10 cm. Unlike the length of the beams of the left and right main beam, the lengths of the left and right brow tines in deer from mountainous and lowland hunting grounds did not show statistically significant differences. The absolute differences in the length of the left frontal tine between these two groups of deer were not statistically significant. In contrast, the analysis showed that there was a statistical difference in the lengths of the right frontal tine. In lowland deer, the average length of the left brow tine was 38.70±7.50 cm, and the right 37.60±6.50 cm. In deer from mountainous regions, the average length of the left brow tine was 37.0±6.30 cm, and the right 37.10±6.60 cm. The authors found that the average length of the left frontal tine in lowland deer was 38.60±7.50 cm, and the right 38.60±8.00 cm. In mountainous deer, the left frontal tine had an average length of 33.60±6.4 cm, and the right 32.30±7.60 cm. The analysis showed a significant statistical difference between the rose circumferences of the left main beam in deer from mountainous and lowland hunting grounds. The same statistical significance was found in the rose circumference between deer from mountainous and lowland hunting grounds. The average rose circumference of the left main beam in lowland deer was 24.50±2.50 cm, and in mountainous deer, it was 24.00±2.90 cm. The average rose circumference of the right main beam in deer from lowland hunting grounds was 24.50 cm±2.50 cm, and in those from mountainous hunting grounds, it was 24.8±3.00 cm.

Hell and Bakoš (1991) analyzed deer trophies at the Nitra (Slovakia) exhibition held in 1990. In a sample of 96 individuals, they found that the average beam length was 110.28 cm, the brow tine 38.97 cm, and the frontal tine 36.62 cm. The average rose

circumference was 26.51 cm. Degmečić (2010), studying deer antlers in the Croatian part of Baranja, found that the average beam length was 105.74 cm. The average length of the frontal tine was 47.54 cm, and the brow tine had an average length of 40.20 cm. The average rose circumference was 25.89 cm. The author notes that the length of the main beam is linearly dependent on the length of all the tines on the beam. This means that the longer the beam, the longer the tines will be.

Urošević B.M. (2015), in a sample of 33 deer antlers from hilly hunting grounds, shot in Serbia, found that the average length of the left beam was 96.04 cm. The right main beam had an average length of 95.91 cm. The left brow tine had an average length of 32.21 cm, while the right brow tine was on average 33.15 cm long. In these deer, the left frontal tine had an average length of 27.02 cm, and the right 28.83 cm. The region in Serbia where the research was conducted is located in the east of the country, near the border with Romania.

Hell (1983) states that the length of the beam and frontal tine reaches its maximum at the age of 12 years in deer in Slovakia. The rose circumference reaches its maximum at the age of 13 years. This research showed that the average beam length of a 12-year-old deer was 103.10 cm. At the same age, the average length of the brow tine was 33.40 cm, and the frontal tine 35.60 cm.

Analyzing the basic morphological parameters of 22 red deer antlers (*Cervus elaphus hippelaphus* L.) hunted during the imperial hunt from 1897-1912, Urošević et al. (2023) determined that the left antler had an average length of 81.84 cm, while the right one was 85.34 cm. Interestingly, their maximum values were identical, each measuring 111.00 cm. Since the minimum values were relatively low, with the left antler at 39.00 cm and the right at 38.00 cm, it can be concluded that young specimens were hunted. The average circumference of the rose on the left antler was 19.61 cm, while on the right it was 19.59 cm.

Materials and Methods

For this research, data were taken from the official catalog (Catalogul trofeelor) of the exhibition held in Bucharest (Expozitia Nationala de Vanatoare) from September 15-21, 1997. Using the random sampling method, data were collected for 40 deer hunted in Romania during the period 1980-1996. The morphometric parameters studied included: length of the left main beam, length of the left brow tine, length of the left befrontal tine, circumference of the left rose, length of the right main beam, length of the right brow tine, length of the right frontal tine, and circumference of the right rose. The data were processed using the method of descriptive statistics. The Pearson correlation method was used to determine the dependence between the observed parameters. The collected data were processed with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows Release 17.0.0 software.

Results

The lengths of the right antler beam range from 101 cm to 131 cm, and the lengths of the left antler beam range from 107 cm to 131 cm. Using the method of descriptive statistics, the mean values of the lengths of the right antler beam $M=115.05$ cm ($SD=7.55836$) and the lengths of the left antler beam $M=117.79$ cm, $SD=6.99654$ were obtained (table 1). The mean value of the length of right brow tine is $M=40.87$ cm ($SD=5.87080$) and of the left brow tine is $M=41.6217$

cm ($SD=5.45201$). The length of right frontal tine range from 26 cm up to 55.2 cm and this tine was long, on the average, 40.52 cm ($SD=6.38242$). The left frontal tine was long, on the average, 41.76 cm ($SD=7.82946$), ranging from 26 cm up to 60.40 cm. Circumference of coronets were very similar, on the average, the circumference of left coronet was 26.98 cm ($SD=1.96371$), and the circumference of right coronet was 27 cm ($SD=1.94537$).

Table 1. Descriptive statistical indicators

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Length of left antler beam	30	107.00	131.00	117.7880	6.99654
Length of right antler beam	30	101.00	131.00	115.0467	7.55836
Length of left brow tine	30	30.50	58.00	41.6217	5.45201
Length of right brow tine	30	27.70	55.80	40.8700	5.87080
Length of left frontal tine	30	26.00	60.40	41.7567	7.82946
Length of right frontal tine	30	26.00	55.20	40.5167	6.38242
Circumference of left coronet	30	23.40	30.80	26.9800	1.96371
Circumference of right coronet	30	23.50	31.20	27.0033	1.94537
Valid N (listwise)	30				

The results of Pearson's correlation showed a statistically significant positive correlation between same morphometric parameters. Namely, in table 2, it can be observed that there is a significant statistical positive correlation between the lengths of the right antler beam

and the length of the left antler beam. The similar correlation is found between length of left brow tine and length of right brow tine; length of left and right frontal tine; and circumference of left and right coronets (table 3,4,5).

Table 2. Correlations between some of measured trophy elements

		Length of right antler beam	Length of left antler beam
Length of right antler beam	Pearson Correlation	1	.863**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
Length of left antler beam	Pearson Correlation	.863**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

Table 3. Correlations between some of measured trophy elements

		Length of left brow tine	Length of right brow tine
Length of left brow tine	Pearson Correlation	1	.872**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
Length of right brow tine	Pearson Correlation	.872**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

Table 4. Correlations between some of measured trophy elements

		Length of left frontal tine	Length of right frontal tine
Length of left frontal tine	Pearson Correlation	1	.767**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
Length of right frontal tine	Pearson Correlation	.767**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

Table 5. Correlations between some of measured trophy elements

		Circumference of left coronet	Circumference of right coronet
Circumference of left coronet	Pearson Correlation	1	.947**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
Circumference of right coronet	Pearson Correlation	.947**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

Conclusion

Using the method of descriptive statistics, the mean values of the basic morphometric parameters in red deer were obtained. Results showed that the right beam was a little shorter than left beam in the observed population. The mean value of the length of the left brow tine is almost similar as right brow tine, as well as lengths of right and left frontal tines. The mean values of the circumference of the left and right coronets are almost the same. The results of Pearson's correlation showed a statistically significant positive correlation just between same morphometric elements on each beam.

References:

1. Degmečić, D. 2010. Blago baranjskog podunavlja. Hrvatski lovački savez, Zagreb.
2. Dragišić, P. 1957. Jelen. Lovačka knjiga. Zagreb.
3. Hell, P. 1983. Rast parožia jelena obyčajneho (Cervus elaphus, L.) v Chranenej polovnej oblasti Polana. Folia Venatoria, 13. str. 35-50
4. Hell, P., Bakoš, A. 1991. Zhodnotenie vyvoja trofejovej kvality raticovej zveri u ČSFR za poslednych 15 Rokov. Folia Venatoria, 21, str. 163-193.
5. Rajskey, M., Pavlik, Š., Rajskey, D. 2003. Rast parožia a trofejova kvaliteta jelenej zveri v podunajskej polovnej oblasti. Folia Venatoria, 33, str. 33-44.

6. Sirbu, G., Simon, D., Ionescu, O., Spataru, C., Sirbu, A. 2020. Antler Size and Form in Relationship with Cranial Architecture in Red Deer (Cervus elaphus L.) a Case Study in the Curvature Carpathians. Proceedings of the International Symposium „Forest and Sustainable Development“, 9th Edition, 16th October 2020, Brasov, Romania, pp. 95-113

7. Urošević, B.M. 2015. Morfološke karakteristike parogova jelena u lovištima istočne i severozapadne Srbije. Specijalistički rad. Univerzitet u Beogradu, Poljoprivredni fakultet.

8. Urošević, M., Milosava Matejević, Tsegmid Namsrajav, Goran Stanišić, Branislav Živković. 2023. Морфометрические характеристики рогов оленя благородного (Cervus elaphus hippelaphus L., 1758), отстрелянного в Беловежской пуце во время царской охоты. 10 Международной Конференции «Сохранение разнообразия животных и охотничье хозяйство России», 13-14/2.2023. Moskva

9. Urošević, M. M., Drobnjak, D., Urošević, B. M., Čeranić, A., Živković, B. 2018. Osnovne morfološke karakteristike parogova jelena (Cervus elaphus) u brdskim i ravničarskim lovištima, (Basic morphological traits of Antlers of Red Deer (Cervus elaphus) from lowland and mountainous Areas) 8 Naučni skup o lovstvu i lovnom turizmu. Zbornik radova, str. 95 - 102. Žagubica.